

STUDY OF FOLKLORE ASPECTS OF UZBEK FOLK PROVERBS.

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Annotation: In this article, the scientific theoretical studies of scientists, scientific researches, the different aspects of proverbs and sayings, the importance of proverbs in folk oral creativity, when and how Uzbek folk proverbs appeared.

One of the factors that express the national values and the culture of the nation, which show the identity of the nation, is the oral creativity of the people. At the moment when intensive research is being conducted on proverbs, we cannot help but be interested in their history. Proverbs have been studied with great interest by folklorists of all nations to this day, and deep research is being conducted on this process even today. Making news about Uzbek proverbs, searching for their unexplored areas is one of the tasks facing Uzbek linguistics today. Today, for young scientists who are conducting research on folklore, especially proverbs, deep knowledge of the history of studying Uzbek proverbs to this day forms the foundation of this article. Uzbek proverbs are distinguished from other folk proverbs by their diversity and color. At the same time, they are the product of the creation of our ancestors who lived in very ancient times. Folk proverbs have been studied many times by linguists, literary scholars, and folklorists as examples of perfect artistic creativity. In our history, we even come across cases in which proverbs were treated from a special, so to speak, folkloristic point of view, albeit episodic in nature. From the above points, it can be understood that proverbs are a genre that expresses the wisdom of the people and is always passed down from generation to generation.

Just as there are no authors of proverbs, when and where they appeared it is not clear. Proverbs, one of the most important genres of folklore, are one of the most important topics studied in linguistics and folklore. Studying and researching proverbs, which are one of the most important genres of folklore, and folk art in general, is of great importance today.

Proverbs are a widespread independent genre of oral artistic creativity as rare examples of folk wisdom. Conditionally, they can be called the rules of public etiquette. After all, proverbs are a phenomenon born from a very concise, concise and figurative expression of socio-political, spiritual-cultural and moral-philosophical views tested by the life experiences of the people over the centuries. Proverbs are not specially created, but arise as a moral evaluation of the conclusion born from the tested life experience due to the requirements of a certain situation. Proverbs show that they are the result of long-term life experiences in the process of people's activities in various fields, they are stable and unchanging correct and true conclusions. Folk art has its own laws and principles of development. These features are studied in the field of paremiology of folklore studies. As we conduct research on proverbs, here we refer to the field of paremiology. Paremia is a Greek word that means wisdom,

proverb, or proverb. Paremiography deals with the collection, recording and publication of examples of folk parameki art. In other collections, the subject-theme classification of proverbs is mainly used. For example, the collection of "Uzbek folk proverbs" presents a topic group of 30 subjects:

- 1) About the homeland and patriotism;
- 2) about work and diligence;
- 3) collectivism;
- 4) about friendship and disagreement;
- 5) about science and art;
- 6) about wisdom and ignorance;
- 7) about courage and humanity;
- 8) about courage and cowardice;
- 9) about vigilance and caution;
- 10) about family and relatives;
- 11) about love and loyalty;
- 12) about respecting elders;
- 13) about humility and education;
- 14) about dignity;
- 15) about guests and hospitality;
- 16) about good words and goodness;
- 17) about honesty and sincerity;
- 18) about prudence and negligence;
- 19) about savings;
- 20) about patience, contentment, perseverance;
- 21) about purity, purity;
- 22) about trust and despair;
- 23) about boasting and arrogance;
- 24) about greed;
- 25) about animals;
- 26) about advice;
- 27) figurative proverbs;
- 28) proverbs of advice;
- 29) poverty and need: proverbs about the historical past;
- 30) proverbs directed against injustice;

It should be noted that the proverbs are divided into several different topics, and the proverbs have been studied by folklorists from the folkloristic point of view. Folklore proverbs were collected, classified and published as a book. The study of proverbs shows the rich history of the Uzbek nation as well as its national culture. The history of the study of Uzbek proverbs: The history of collecting and studying Uzbek folk masterpieces, proverbs, which are one of the popular genres of Uzbek folk art, as well as the use of them by writers and scholars in their works, dates back to a long time ago. . So it can be assumed that a thousand years ago, our ancestors called proverbs "sav". Later, in the works of Alisher Navoi, the term proverb was given in the form of "parable". In one of his works, Navoi says that "my masaldurkim is sleep is death." It is known that the term "parable" was used until the beginning of the 20th century. From the second quarter of the last century, the word proverb

began to appear a lot. Later, from the middle of the 20th century, only in the form of a proverb applied. Interest in the proverb from a literary point of view, its use in order to increase the artistry of the work and ensure the fluency of the artistic language has always been in the attention of the word artists. Yusuf Khos Hajib, Ahmed Yassavi, Rabguzi, Lutfi, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Abulghozi Bahadirkhan, Munis, Ogahi, Nadira, If you carefully study the works of Muqimi, Furqat, Avaz, Hamza, Sadriddin Ainiy, Fitrat, Cholpon, Abdulla Qadiri, Oybek, Gafur Ghulam and dozens of other artists, you will find how many proverbs, sometimes exactly, we can sometimes see it used interchangeably. The extensive use of proverbs in works of art has always helped to enrich the language of the work. For centuries, folk proverbs have attracted the attention of great and well-known writers as examples of folk oral creativity, rare in terms of their form and content. From Yusuf Khos Hajib to Muqimi, from Alisher Navoi to Aibek, they used folk proverbs effectively. Among them: Alisher Navoi's lyrics "Get out of hope", "The dog stayed, the caravan moved", "When I say firoqdin, ul der Iroqdin"; In Babur's works: "There are four on the path of my two eyes", "I was like you, you will be like me"; "The death of a horse, the holiday of a dog", "A dry spoon tears the mouth" in the works of Abdulla Qahhor; In the epic "Alpomish" there are many proverbs such as "The sultan does not insult his bone", "A woman who goes to the sieve has fifty words."

In the science of folklore studies, the use of folk proverbs by poets and writers in the text of works is called folklorism. This situation shows that the artist's attitude towards folk art is positive. So, the proverbs created by our people are deep in terms of content as well as in terms of art is perfect. It turns out that the proverbs created by our people can be used not only in terms of content, but also in terms of art, as examples of excellent verbal art. There was a demand to collect proverbs created over the centuries and work as a certain complex. If proverbs had not been collected by scientists and turned into a certain complex, there would be no basis for our work on this topic. The work of collecting Uzbek folk proverbs and working as a certain collection began from ancient times. Scholars report that our proverbs and sayings were compiled by order of one of the ancient kings, Abbas Safavid. Unfortunately, this complex has not reached today. At this point, we would like to emphasize that there are also works based on proverbs in the history of our literature. For example, Muhammad Sharif Gulkhani's work "Zarbulmasal" contains more than 300 Uzbek folk proverbs. Basically, the great scholar of the 11th century M. Kashgari widely used proverbs of peoples belonging to the Turkish language family in his work "Devonu lughatit turk". .

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